

HYBRID ALGORITHM FOR NONLINEAR EQUILIBRIUM, VARIATIONAL INEQUALITY AND FIXED POINT PROBLEMS.

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce an iterative process which converges strongly to a common element of sets of solutions of finite family of generalized equilibrium problems, sets of fixed points of finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and sets of zeros of finite family of γ -inverse strongly monotone mappings in Banach spaces. Our theorems improve and generalize several results which are announced recently. Our iteration process, method of proof and corollaries are of independent interest.

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INTRODUCTION

Let E be a real Banach space with dual E^* . We denote by J the normalized duality mapping from E to 2^{E^*} defined by

$$Jx := \{f^* \in E^* : \langle x, f^* \rangle = \|x\|^2 = \|f^*\|^2\},$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the generalized duality pairing between members of E and members of E^* . It is well known that if E^* is strictly convex then J is single valued and if E is uniformly smooth then J is uniformly continuous on bounded subsets of E . Moreover, if E is reflexive and strictly convex Banach space with a strictly convex dual, then J^{-1} is single valued, one-to-one, surjective, and it is the duality mapping from E^* into E and thus $JJ^{-1} = I_{E^*}$ and $J^{-1}J = I_E$ (see e.g., [5, 20]).

Remark 1. If $E = l_p$, $1 < p < \infty$, then J is given explicitly as $Jx = \|x\|_{l_p}^{2-p} y \in l_q$, $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, $y = \{x_1|x_1|^{p-2}, x_2|x_2|^{p-2}, \dots\}$, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and so J^{-1} is also easily computed. Furthermore, if $E = L_p$, $Jx = \|x\|_{L_p}^{2-p} |x|^{p-2}x \in L_q$, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ (see e.g., [1]). Observe that if H is a Hilbert space, then $E^* = H$, J and J^{-1} becomes the identity operator on H .

Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Banach space E . Let $f : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a bifunction, where \mathbb{R} is the set of real numbers, and $B : C \rightarrow E^*$ be a nonlinear mapping. The generalized equilibrium problem (for short, *GEP*) for f and B is to find $u \in C$ such that

$$f(u, v) + \langle Bu, v - u \rangle \geq 0, \forall v \in C. \quad (1)$$

The set of solutions for the problem (1) is denoted by $GEP(f, B)$, i.e.,

$$GEP(f, B) := \{u \in C : f(u, v) + \langle Bu, v - u \rangle \geq 0, \forall v \in C\}.$$

If $B = 0$ in (1), then $GEP(1)$ reduces to the classical equilibrium problem (for short, *EP*) and $GEP(f, 0)$ is denoted by $EP(f)$, i.e.,

$$EP(f) = \{u \in C : f(u, v) \geq 0, \forall v \in C\}.$$

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If $f = 0$ in (1), then $GEP(1)$ reduces to the classical variational inequality problem and $GEP(0, B)$ is denoted by $VI(B, C)$, i.e.,

$$VI(B, C) = \{u^* \in C : \langle Bu^*, v - u^* \rangle \geq 0, \forall v \in C\}.$$

The problem (1) is very general in the sense that it includes, as special cases, optimization problems, variational inequalities, min-max problems, the Nash equilibrium problems in non-cooperative games and countless of others; (see, for instance, [2, 12])

A mapping $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E^*$, is said to be monotone if for each $x, y \in D(A)$, the following inequality holds:

$$\langle x - y, Ax - Ay \rangle \geq 0. \tag{2}$$

A is said to be γ -inverse strongly monotone if there exists a positive real number γ such that

$$\langle x - y, Ax - Ay \rangle \geq \gamma \|Ax - Ay\|^2, \text{ for all } x, y \in K. \tag{3}$$

If A is γ -inverse strongly monotone, then it is Lipschitz continuous with constant $\frac{1}{\gamma}$, that is, $\|Ax - Ay\| \leq \frac{1}{\gamma} \|x - y\|$, for all $x, y \in D(A)$, and hence uniformly continuous.

Let E be a smooth real Banach space. The function $\phi : E \times E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\phi(x, y) = \|x\|^2 - 2 \langle x, Jy \rangle + \|y\|^2 \text{ for all } x, y \in E, \tag{4}$$

is studied by Alber [1], Kamimura and Takahashi [8], and Riech [16]. It is obvious from the definition of the function ϕ that

$$(\|x\| - \|y\|)^2 \leq \phi(x, y) \leq (\|x\| + \|y\|)^2 \text{ for } x, y \in E. \tag{5}$$

Observe that in a Hilbert space H , (5) reduces to $\phi(x, y) = \|x - y\|^2$, for $x, y \in H$.

Let E be a reflexive, strictly convex and smooth real Banach space and let C be a nonempty closed and convex subset of E . The generalized projection mapping, introduced by Alber [1], is a mapping $\Pi_C : E \rightarrow C$, that assigns to an arbitrary point $y \in E$ the minimum point of the functional $\phi(\cdot, y)$, that is $\Pi_C y = \bar{x}$, where \bar{x} is the solution to the minimization problem

$$\phi(\bar{x}, y) = \min\{\phi(x, y), x \in C\}. \tag{6}$$

In fact, we have the following result.

Lemma 1. [1] Let C be a nonempty closed and convex subset of a reflexive, strictly convex, and smooth real Banach space E and let $y \in E$. Then there exists a unique element $x_0 \in C$ such that $\phi(x_0, y) = \min\{\phi(z, y) : z \in C\}$.

Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of E , and let T be a mapping from C into itself. We denote by $F(T)$ the set of fixed points of T . A point $p \in C$ is said to be an asymptotic fixed point of T [16] if C contains a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ which converges weakly to p such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - Tx_n\| = 0$. The set of asymptotic fixed points of T will be denoted by $\tilde{F}(T)$. The asymptotic behavior of relatively nonexpansive mapping was studied in [3, 4]. A mapping T from C into itself is said to be relatively nonexpansive [18, 27] if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (R1) $F(T) \neq \emptyset$;
- (R2) $\phi(p, Tx) \leq \phi(p, x), \forall x \in C, p \in F(T)$;
- (R3) $F(T) = \tilde{F}(T)$.

If E is a smooth, strictly convex and reflexive real Banach space, and $A \subset E \times E^*$ is a continuous monotone mapping with $A^{-1}(0) \neq \emptyset$ then it proved in [9] that $J_r := (J + rA)^{-1}J$, for $r > 0$ is relatively nonexpansive. Moreover, if C is nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth, strictly convex, and reflexive Banach E , and $T : C \rightarrow C$ is relatively nonexpansive then $F(T)$ is closed and convex (see, [10]).

Let $f : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a bifunction. The equilibrium problem for f is to find $x^* \in C$ such that

$$f(x^*, y) \geq 0, \forall y \in C. \tag{7}$$

The set of solutions of (7) is denoted by $EP(f)$. For solving the equilibrium problem for a bifunction $f : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, let us assume that f satisfies the following conditions:

- (A1) $f(x, x) = 0$ for all $x \in C$,
- (A2) f is monotone, that is, $f(x, y) + f(y, x) \leq 0$ for all $x, y \in C$,
- (A3) for each $x, y, z \in C$, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} f(tz + (1-t)x, y) \leq f(x, y)$,
- (A4) for each $x \in C, y \mapsto f(x, y)$ is convex and lower semicontinuous.

Many authors studied the problem of finding a common element of the set of fixed points of nonexpansive and / or relatively nonexpansive mappings and the set of solutions of an equilibrium problem in the frame work of Hilbert spaces and Banach spaces respectively: see, for instance, [15, 16, 26, 23, 27, 13, 14] and the references therein. For finding an element of $F(S) \cap VI(A, C)$, Takahashi and Toyoda [21] introduced the following iterative scheme:

$$x_{n+1} = \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n)SP_C(x_n - \lambda_n Ax_n), \quad n \geq 1, \tag{8}$$

where $x_0 \in C$, P_C is a metric projection of H onto C , $\{\alpha_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in $(0, 1)$ and $\{\lambda_n\}$ is a sequence in $(0, 2\alpha)$, where α is strong monotonicity constant of A .

Recently, Iiduka and Takahashi [7] introduced the following iterative scheme:

$$x_{n+1} = \alpha_n u + \beta_n x_n + \gamma_n SP_C(x_n - \lambda_n Ax_n), \quad n \geq 1, \tag{9}$$

where $u, x_0 \in C$, and proved the strong convergence theorems for iterative scheme (9) under some conditions on parameters. Furthermore, Tada and Takahashi [19] introduced the Mann type iterative algorithm for finding a common element of the $EP(f)$ and the set of the common fixed points of nonexpansive mapping and obtained the weak convergence of the Mann type iterative algorithm. In 2007, Yao, Liou and Yao [25] introduced an iterative process for finding a common element of the set of solutions of the $EP(f)$ and the set of common fixed points of infinitely many nonexpansive mappings in Hilbert spaces. They proved a strong convergence theorem under mild conditions on iterative parameters. Very recently, Moudafi [11] proposed an iterative algorithm for finding a common element of $GEP(f, B) \cap F(S)$, where $B : C \rightarrow H$ is an α -inverse strongly monotone mapping, and obtained a weak convergence theorem.

In this paper, it is our aim to introduce an iterative process for finding a common element of sets of solutions of finite family of generalized equilibrium problem, sets of fixed points of finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and sets of zeros of finite family of γ -inverse strongly monotone mappings in Banach spaces.

PRELIMINARIES

Let E be a normed linear space with $\dim E \geq 2$. The *modulus of smoothness* of E is the function $\rho_E : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ defined by

$$\rho_E(\tau) := \sup \left\{ \frac{\|x + y\| + \|x - y\|}{2} - 1 : \|x\| = 1; \|y\| = \tau \right\}.$$

The space E is said to be smooth if $\rho_E(\tau) > 0, \forall \tau > 0$ and E is called *uniformly smooth* if and only if $\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{\rho_E(\tau)}{\tau} = 0$.

The *modulus of convexity* of E is the function $\delta_E : (0, 2] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by

$$\delta_E(\epsilon) := \inf \left\{ 1 - \left\| \frac{x + y}{2} \right\| : \|x\| = \|y\| = 1; \epsilon = \|x - y\| \right\}.$$

E is called *uniformly convex* if and only if $\delta_E(\epsilon) > 0$ for every $\epsilon \in (0, 2]$. Let $p > 1$. Then E is said to be *p-uniformly convex* if there exists a constant $c > 0$ such that $\delta(\epsilon) \geq c\epsilon^p$ for all $\epsilon \in [0, 2]$. Observe that every p-uniformly convex Banach space is uniformly convex real Banach space.

It is well known (see for example [24]) that

$$L_p(l_p) \text{ or } W_m^p \text{ is } \begin{cases} p - \text{uniformly convex} & \text{if } p \geq 2; \\ 2 - \text{uniformly convex} & \text{if } 1 < p \leq 2. \end{cases}$$

In the sequel, we shall make use of the following definitions and lemmas.

Lemma 2. [24] If E is a uniformly convex real Banach space, then there exists a continuous, strictly increasing and convex function $g : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, $g(0) = 0$, such that for all $x, y \in B_r(0) := \{x \in E : \|x\| \leq r\}$ and for any $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$\|\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y\|^2 \leq \alpha \|x\|^2 + (1 - \alpha) \|y\|^2 - \alpha(1 - \alpha)g(\|x - y\|).$$

Lemma 3. [24] Let E be a 2-uniformly convex real Banach space. Then for all $x, y \in E$, we have

$$\|x - y\| \leq \frac{2}{c^2} \|Jx - Jy\|. \tag{10}$$

where J is the normalized duality mapping of E and $0 < c < 1$.

Lemma 4. [1] Let C be a nonempty closed and convex subset of a reflexive, strictly convex, and smooth real Banach space E and let $x \in E$. Then $\forall y \in C$,

$$\phi(y, \Pi_C x) + \phi(\Pi_C x, x) \leq \phi(y, x).$$

Lemma 5. [8] Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth, uniformly convex Banach space E . Let $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ and $\{y_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ be sequences in E such that either $\{x_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ or $\{y_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is bounded. If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi(x_n, y_n) = 0$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - y_n\| = 0$.

Lemma 6. [1] Let C be a convex subset of a smooth real Banach space E . Let $x \in E$. Then $x_0 = \Pi_C x$ if and only if

$$\langle z - x_0, Jx_0 - Jx \rangle \geq 0, \forall z \in C.$$

We denote by $N_C(v)$ the normal cone for C at a point $v \in C$, that is $N_C(v) := \{x^* \in E^* : \langle v - y, x^* \rangle \geq 0 \text{ for all } y \in C\}$. In the sequel we shall use the following lemma.

Lemma 7. (Rockafellar [17]) Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Banach space E and let A be a monotone and hemicontinuous operator of C into E^* with $C = D(A)$. Let $B \subset E \times E^*$ be an operator defined as follows:

$$Bv := \begin{cases} Av + N_C(v), & v \in C, \\ \emptyset, & v \in C. \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

Then B is maximal monotone and $B^{-1}(0) = VI(A, C)$.

We make use of the function $V : E \times E^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$V(x, x^*) = \|x\|^2 - 2 \langle x, x^* \rangle + \|x^*\|^2, \text{ for all } x \in E \text{ and } x^* \in E^*,$$

studied by Alber [1]. That is $V(x, x^*) = \phi(x, J^{-1}x^*)$ for all $x \in E$ and $x^* \in E^*$. We know the following Lemma.

Lemma 8. [1] Let E be a reflexive strictly convex and smooth real Banach space with E^* as its dual. Then

$$V(x, x^*) + 2 \langle j^{-1}x^* - x, y^* \rangle \leq V(x, x^* + y^*),$$

for all $x \in E$ and $x^*, y^* \in E^*$.

Lemma 9. [2] Let C be closed convex subset of a smooth strictly convex and reflexive real Banach space E . Let f be a bifunction from $C \times C$ to \mathbb{R} satisfying (A1)-(A4). Then, for $r > 0$ and $x \in E$, there exists $z \in C$ such that

$$f(z, y) + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, Jz - Jx \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C. \tag{12}$$

Remark 2. Replacing x with $J^{-1}(Jx - rB(x))$ in (12), where B is monotone mapping from C into E^* , then there exists $z \in C$ such that

$$f(z, y) + \langle Bx, y - z \rangle + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, Jz - Jx \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C.$$

By a similar argument of the proof of Lemma 2.8 and Remark 2.9 of [22], we have the following Lemmas.

Lemma 10. [23] Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth, strictly convex and reflexive real Banach space E . Let F be a bifunction from $C \times C$ to \mathbb{R} satisfying (A1)-(A4) and $B : C \rightarrow E^*$ be a monotone mapping. For $r > 0$ and $x \in E$, define a mapping $T_r : E \rightarrow C$ as follows:

$$T_r x := \{z \in C : f(z, y) + \langle Bx, y - z \rangle + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, Jz - Jx \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C\}$$

for all $x \in E$. Then the following hold:

- (1) T_r is single valued
- (2) T_r is firmly nonexpansive type mapping, i.e., for all $x, y \in E$,

$$\langle T_r x - T_r y, JT_r x - JT_r y \rangle \leq \langle T_r x - T_r y, Jx - Jy \rangle;$$

- (3) $F(T_r) = GEP(F, B)$;
- (4) $GEP(F, B)$ is closed and convex.

Lemma 11. [23] Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a smooth, strictly convex and reflexive Banach space E . Let F be a bifunction from $C \times C$ to \mathbb{R} satisfying (A1)-(A4). For $r > 0$, $x \in E$ and $p \in F(T_r)$, we have that

$$\phi(q, T_r x) + \phi(T_r x, x) \leq \phi(q, x).$$

RESULTS

Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be bifunctions and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants $\gamma_i \in (0, 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$; then in what follows, we shall study the following iteration process.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 \in C_0 = C, \quad \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ z_n = \Pi_C J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1} x_n), \\ y_n = J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n) JT_{n+1} z_n); u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \langle B_1 y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, Ju_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \langle B_2 y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, Jv_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta) Jv_n), \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)\}, \\ x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{array} \right. \tag{13}$$

where $A_n = A_{n \pmod m}$, $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and J is the normalized duality mapping on E ; $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$; and $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in $[a, b]$ for some $0 < a < b < \frac{c^2 \gamma}{2}$, where c is the 2-uniformly convex constant of E and $\gamma = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} \gamma_i$.

We shall define

$$T_{k,r} x := \{z \in C : f_k(z, y) + \langle B_k x, y - z \rangle + \frac{1}{r} \langle y - z, Jz - Jx \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C\}$$

for all $x \in E, k = 1, 2$.

Lemma 12. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of relatively nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be a finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants

$$\gamma_i \in (0, 1), i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \text{ Let } F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset \text{ and let } \{x_n\}$$

be a sequence defined by (13). Then the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is well defined for each $n \geq 0$.

Proof. We first show that C_n is closed and convex for all $n \geq 1$. It is obvious that $C_0 = C$ is closed and convex from the definition. Suppose that C_n is closed convex for some $n \geq 1$. From the definition of C_{n+1} , we have that $z \in C_{n+1}$ implies $\phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)$. This is equivalent to

$$\|z\|^2 - 2 \langle z, Jw_n \rangle + \|w_n\|^2 \leq \|z\|^2 - 2 \langle z, Jx_n \rangle + \|x_n\|^2$$

$$\text{Which gives } 2(\langle z, Jx_n \rangle - \langle z, Jw_n \rangle) = 2(\langle z, Jx_n - Jw_n \rangle) - \|x_n\|^2 + \|w_n\|^2 \leq 0$$

It follows that C_{n+1} is closed and convex, hence $\Pi_{C_{n+1}}$ is well defined for all $n \geq 0$.

Next we prove that $F \subset C_n$ for all $n \geq 0$. From the assumption, we see that $F \subset C_0 = C$. Suppose that $F \subset C_n$ for some $n \geq 1$. Now, for $p \in F$, the property of G and Lemma 2 give that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, w_n) &= \phi(p, J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n)) \\ &= \|p\|^2 - 2 \langle p, \beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n \rangle + \|\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n\|^2 \\ &\leq \|p\|^2 - 2\beta \langle p, Ju_n \rangle - 2(1 - \beta) \langle p, Jv_n \rangle + \beta \|Ju_n\|^2 + (1 - \beta) \|Jv_n\|^2 \\ &= \beta \phi(p, u_n) + (1 - \beta) \phi(p, v_n) \\ &= \beta \phi(p, T_{1,r_n}y_n) + (1 - \beta) \phi(p, T_{2,r_n}y_n) \\ &\leq \beta \phi(p, y_n) + (1 - \beta) \phi(p, y_n) = \phi(p, y_n) \\ &= \phi(p, J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n)) \\ &= \|p\|^2 - 2 \langle p, \alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n \rangle + \|\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n\|^2 \\ &\leq \|p\|^2 - 2\alpha_n \langle p, Jx_n \rangle - 2(1 - \alpha_n) \langle p, JT_{n+1}z_n \rangle + \alpha_n \|Jx_n\|^2 \\ &\quad + (1 - \alpha_n) \|JT_{n+1}z_n\|^2 \\ &= \alpha_n \phi(p, x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n) \phi(p, T_{n+1}z_n) \\ &\leq \alpha_n \phi(p, x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n) \phi(p, z_n). \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Moreover, by Lemma 4 and Lemma 8 we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, z_n) &= \phi(p, \Pi_C J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n)) \\ &\leq \phi(p, J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n)) \\ &= V(p, Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) \\ &\leq V(p, (Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) + \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - 2 \langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - p, \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &= V(p, Jx_n) - 2\lambda_n \langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - p, A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &= \phi(p, Jx_n) - 2\lambda_n \langle x_n - p, A_{n+1}x_n \rangle - 2\lambda_n \langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &\leq \phi(p, x_n) - 2\lambda_n \langle x_n - p, A_{n+1}x_n \rangle + 2 \langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, -\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Thus, since $p \in \cap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0)$ and $\gamma = \min \gamma_i$, we have that

$$\langle x - p, A_i x \rangle \geq \gamma \|A_i x\|^2 \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

Thus, we have from (15) that

$$\phi(p, z_n) \leq \phi(p, x_n) - 2\lambda_n \gamma \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2 + 2 \langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, -\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \tag{16}$$

Therefore, from (10), (16) and $\lambda_n \leq \frac{c^2 \gamma}{2}$ we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, z_n) &\leq \phi(p, x_n) - 2\lambda_n \gamma \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2 + \frac{4\lambda_n^2}{c^2} \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2 \\ &= \phi(p, x_n) + 2\lambda_n \left(\frac{2}{c^2} \lambda_n - \gamma \right) \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2 \leq \phi(p, x_n). \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Substituting (17) into (14), we have

$$\phi(p, w_n) \leq \phi(p, x_n),$$

that is $p \in C_{n+1}$. This implies, by induction, that $F \subset C_n$ and the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ generated by (13) is well defined for all $n \geq 0$. ■

Theorem 1. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C, j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be a finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants $\gamma_i \in (0, 1), i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by (13). Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ converges to some element of F .

Proof. We have from Lemma 12 that $F \subset C_n, \forall n \geq 0$ and x_n is well defined for each $n \geq 0$. From $x_n = \Pi_{C_n}(x_0)$, and Lemma 4, we have

$$\phi(p, x_0) = \phi(\Pi_{C_n} x_0, x_0) \leq \phi(p, x_0) - \phi(p, x_n) \leq \phi(p, x_0),$$

for each $p \in F \subset C_n$ and $n \geq 0$. Thus the sequence $\{\phi(x_n, x_0)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is bounded.

Furthermore, since $x_n = \Pi_{C_n}(x_0)$ and $x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0) \in C_{n+1} \subset C_n$ we have that

$$\phi(x_n, x_0) \leq \phi(x_{n+1}, x_0), \forall n \geq 0,$$

which implies that $\{\phi(x_n, x_0)\}_{n \geq 0}$ is increasing and hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi(x_n, x_0)$ exists. Similarly, by Lemma 4, we have, for any positive integer l , that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x_{n+l}, x_n) &= \phi(x_{n+l}, \Pi_{C_n} x_0) \\ &\leq \phi(x_{n+l}, x_0) - \phi(\Pi_{C_n} x_0, x_0) \\ &= \phi(x_{n+l}, x_0) - \phi(x_n, x_0) \forall n \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi(x_n, x_0)$ exists, we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi(x_{n+l}, x_n) = 0$. Thus, Lemma 5 implies that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n+l} - x_n\| = 0, \tag{18}$$

and hence $\{x_n\}$ is Cauchy. Therefore, there exists a point $x^* \in C$ such that $x_n \rightarrow x^*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Since $x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}} x_0 \in C_{n+1}$, we have $\phi(x_{n+1}, w_n) \leq \phi(x_{n+1}, x_n), \forall n \geq 0$.

Thus, by (18) and Lemma 5 we get that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n+1} - w_n\| = 0, \tag{19}$$

and hence $\|x_n - w_n\| \leq \|x_n - x_{n+1}\| + \|x_{n+1} - w_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, which implies that $w_n \rightarrow x^*$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, the uniform continuity of J on bounded sets, gives that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|Jx_{n+l} - Jw_n\| = 0, \tag{20}$$

We note that if E is uniformly smooth then E^* is uniformly convex. Thus, using property of ϕ and Lemma 2 we have, for all $p \in F$, that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, y_n) &= \phi(p, J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n)) \\ &= \|p\|^2 - 2 \langle p, \alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n \rangle + \|\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n\|^2 \\ &\leq \|p\|^2 - 2\alpha_n \langle p, Jx_n \rangle - 2(1 - \alpha_n) \langle p, JT_{n+1}z_n \rangle + \alpha_n \|Jx_n\|^2 + (1 - \alpha_n) \|JT_{n+1}z_n\|^2 \\ &\quad - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|) \\ &= \alpha_n \phi(p, x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n) \phi(p, T_{n+1}z_n) - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|) \\ &\leq \alpha_n \phi(p, x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n) \phi(p, z_n) - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|), \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Thus, from (17) and (21) we have that

$$\phi(p, y_n) \leq \phi(p, x_n) + 2(1 - \alpha_n)\lambda_n \left(\frac{2}{c^2} \lambda_n - \gamma \right) \|A_{n+1}\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|) \tag{22}$$

On the other hand from Lemma 11 we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, w_n) &= \phi(p, J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Ju_n)) \\ &\leq \beta\phi(p, u_n) + (1 - \beta)\phi(p, v_n) \\ &= \beta\phi(p, T_{1,r}y_n) + (1 - \beta)\phi(p, T_{2,r}y_n) \leq \phi(p, y_n). \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Substituting (22) into (23) we get that

$$\phi(p, w_n) \leq \phi(p, x_n) + 2(1 - \alpha_n)\lambda_n \left(\frac{2}{c^2}\lambda_n - \gamma \right) \|A_{n+1}\|^2 - \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|). \tag{24}$$

Now, using the fact that $\lambda_n < \frac{c^2\gamma}{2}$, the inequality (24) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n)g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|) &\leq \phi(p, x_n) - \phi(p, w_n) \\ &= \|p\|^2 - 2\langle p, Jx_n \rangle + \|x_n\|^2 - \|p\|^2 + 2\langle p, Jw_n \rangle - \|w_n\|^2 \\ &= \|x_n\|^2 - \|w_n\|^2 - 2\langle p, Jx_n - Jw_n \rangle \\ &\leq \|x_n - w_n\| (\|x_n\| + \|w_n\|) + 2\|p\| \|Jx_n - Jw_n\| \\ &\leq M_0(\|x_n - w_n\| + \|Jx_n - Jw_n\|), \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

for some $M_0 > 0$. Thus, since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - w_n\| = 0$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|Jx_n - Jw_n\| = 0$ and we obtain

$$\phi(p, x_n) - \phi(p, w_n) \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty, \tag{26}$$

and hence inequality (25) implies that $g(\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\|) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, from the property of g we get that $\|Jx_n - JT_{n+1}z_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Furthermore, since J^{-1} is also uniformly norm-to-norm continuous on bounded sets, we see that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_{n+1}z_n\| = 0. \tag{27}$$

Moreover, from (24) we have that

$$(1 - \alpha_n)2\lambda_n \left(\gamma - \frac{2}{c^2}\lambda_n \right) \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2 \leq \phi(p, x_n) - \phi(p, w_n)$$

which yields that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|A_{n+1}x_n\| = 0 \tag{28}$$

Now, Lemma 4, Lemma 8 and (17) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x_n, z_n) &= \phi(x_n, \Pi_C J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n)) \\ &\leq \phi(x_n, J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n)) \\ &= V(x_n, Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) \\ &= V(x_n, (Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) + \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - 2\langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &= \phi(x_n, x_n) + 2\langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, -\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &= 2\langle J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - x_n, -\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n \rangle \\ &\leq 2\|J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n) - J^{-1}Jx_n\| \|\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n\| \\ &= 2\|J^{-1}\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n\| \|\lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n\| \\ &\leq \frac{4b^2}{c^2} \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

that is

$$\phi(x_n, z_n) \leq \frac{4b^2}{c^2} \|A_{n+1}x_n\|^2. \tag{29}$$

It follows from (28), (29) and Lemma 5 that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - z_n\| = 0; \tag{30}$$

and hence $z_n \rightarrow p$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

We now show that $p \in \bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j)$. Observe that from (27) and (30) we obtain that

$$\|T_{n+1}z_n - z_n\| \leq \|T_{n+1}z_n - x_n\| + \|z_n - x_n\| \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T_{n+1}z_n = p. \tag{31}$$

Let $\{n_l\}_{l \geq 1} \subset \mathbb{N}$ be such that $T_{n_l+1} = T_1$ for all $l \in \mathbb{N}$, then since $z_{n_l} \rightarrow p$ as $l \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain from (31), using continuity of T_1 , that

$$p = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} T_{n_l+1}z_{n_l} = \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} T_1z_{n_l} = T_1p.$$

Similarly, if $\{n_k\}_{k \geq 1} \subset \mathbb{N}$ is such that $T_{n_k+1} = T_2$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, then we have again that

$$p = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T_{n_k+1}z_{n_k} = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T_2z_{n_k} = T_2p.$$

Continuing, we obtain that $T_j p = p$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$. Hence, $p \in \bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j)$.

Next we show that $p \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0)$. Since A_i is γ -inverse strongly monotone for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have that A_i is $\frac{1}{\gamma}$ -Lipschitz continuous. Thus,

$$\|A_{n+1}x_n - A_{n+1}p\| \leq \frac{1}{\gamma} \|x_n - p\| \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{32}$$

Hence, from (32) and (28), we obtain that

$$\|A_{n+1}p\| \leq \|A_{n+1}x_n - A_{n+1}p\| + \|A_{n+1}x_n\| \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Consequently, we get that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A_{n+1}p = 0.$$

Let $\{n_s\}_{s \geq 1} \subset \mathbb{N}$ be such that $A_{n_s+1} = A_1$ for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, $A_1 p = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} A_{n_s+1}p = 0$.

Similarly, we have that $A_i p = 0$ for $i = 2, \dots, m$. Thus, $p \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0)$.

Furthermore, we show that $p \in \bigcap GEP(f_k, B_k) = F(T_{k,r})$, $k = 1, 2$. Let $p \in F$. From $u_n = T_{1,r_n}y_n$, Lemma 11, (21) and the fact that $x_n \rightarrow p$, $z_n \rightarrow p$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(p, u_n) &= \phi(p, T_{1,r_n}y_n) \leq \phi(p, y_n) \\ &\leq \alpha_n \phi(p, x_n) + (1 - \alpha_n) \phi(p, z_n) \\ &\leq \phi(p, x_n) + \phi(p, z_n) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Thus, by Lemma 5 and (33), $u_n \rightarrow p$ and $y_n \rightarrow p$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. These imply that,

$$\|u_n - y_n\| \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Consequently, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|Ju_n - Jy_n\| = 0$. Hence,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|Ju_n - Jy_n\|}{r_n} = 0. \tag{34}$$

But from (A2) we note that

$$\langle B_1 y_n, v - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle v - u_n, Ju_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq -f_1(u_n, v) \geq f_1(v, u_n) \forall v \in C,$$

and hence

$$\langle B_1 y_n, v - u_n \rangle + \left\langle v - u_n, \frac{J u_n - J y_n}{r_n} \right\rangle \geq f_1(v, u_n) \quad \forall v \in C. \tag{35}$$

Put $z_t = tv + (1 - t)p$ for all $t \in (0, 1]$ and $v \in C$.

Consequently, we get that $z_t \in C$. From (35), it follows that

$$\langle B_1 z_t, z_t - u_n \rangle - \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - u_n \rangle \geq -\langle B_1 y_n, z_t - u_n \rangle - \left\langle z_t - u_n, \frac{J u_n - J y_n}{r_n} \right\rangle + f_1(z_t, u_n)$$

This implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - u_n \rangle &\geq \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - u_n \rangle - \langle B_1 y_n, z_t - u_n \rangle - \left\langle z_t - u_n, \frac{J u_n - J y_n}{r_n} \right\rangle + f_1(z_t, u_n) \\ &= \langle B_1 z_t - B_1 u_n, z_t - u_n \rangle + \langle B_1 u_n - B_1 y_n, z_t - u_n \rangle \\ &\quad - \left\langle z_t - u_n, \frac{J u_n - J y_n}{r_n} \right\rangle + f_1(z_t, u_n). \end{aligned}$$

By the continuity of B_1 and the fact that $u_n \rightarrow p, y_n \rightarrow p$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain that

$$B_1 u_n - B_1 y_n \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \tag{36}$$

Since B_1 is monotone, we have that $\langle B_1 z_t - B_1 u_n, z_t - u_n \rangle \geq 0$. Using this, (34) and (36), it follows from (A4) and (36) that

$$f_1(z_t, p) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_1(z_t, u_n) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - u_n \rangle = \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - p \rangle.$$

Now, from (A1) and (A4) we get that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= f_1(z_t, z_t) \leq t f_1(z_t, v) + (1 - t) f_1(z_t, p) \\ &\leq t f_1(z_t, v) + (1 - t) \langle B_1 z_t, z_t - p \rangle \\ &\leq t f_1(z_t, v) + (1 - t) \langle B_1 z_t, tv + (1 - t)p - p \rangle \\ &= t f_1(z_t, v) + (1 - t)t \langle B_1 z_t, v - p \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

and hence

$$f_1(z_t, v) + (1 - t) \langle B_1 z_t, v - p \rangle \geq 0.$$

Letting $t \rightarrow 0$, we have

$$f_1(p, v) + \langle B_1 p, v - p \rangle \geq 0.$$

This implies that $p \in GEP(f_1, B_1)$. Similarly, considering $v_n = T_{2,r_n} y_n$, the same argument gives that $p \in GEP(f_2, B_2)$.

Finally, we prove that $p = \Pi_F(x_0)$. From $x_n = \Pi_{C_n}(x_0)$, we have

$$\langle J x_0 - J x_n, x_n - z \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall z \in C_n.$$

Since $F \in C_n$, we also have that

$$\langle J x_0 - J x_n, x_n - p \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall p \in F. \tag{37}$$

By taking limits in (37), one has

$$\langle J x_0 - J x^*, x^* - p \rangle \geq 0, \quad \forall p \in F.$$

Now, by Lemma 6 we have that $x^* = \Pi_F x_0$. This completes the proof. ■

Strong convergence theorem for approximating a common element of sets of solutions of two generalized equilibrium problems and the sets of fixed points of finite family of relatively nonexpansive mappings in Banach spaces may not require that E is a 2-uniformly convex real Banach space. In fact, we have the following Theorem.

Theorem 2. *Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C, j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 \in C_0 = C, \quad \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}x_n); u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \langle B_1y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, Ju_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \langle B_2y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, Jv_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n), \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)\}, \\ x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (38)$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and J is the normalized duality mapping on E ; $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ converges to some element of F .

Proof. Put $A_i \equiv 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ in Theorem 1. Then, we get that $z_n = x_n$; and the method of proof of Theorem 1 gives the required assertion without the requirement that E is a 2-uniformly convex real Banach space. ■

If, in Theorem 2, we have that $B_1 \equiv B_2 \equiv 0$, then we get the following corollary

Corollary 1. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4). Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C, j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 EP(f_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 \in C_0 = C, \quad \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}x_n); u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, Ju_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, Jv_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n), \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)\}, \\ x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (39)$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and J is the normalized duality mapping on E ; $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ converges to some element of F .

If, in Theorem 2, we have that $f_1 \equiv f_2 \equiv 0$, then we have the following corollary.

Corollary 2. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C, j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 VI(B_k, C) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 \in C_0 = C, \quad \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}x_n); u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ \langle B_1y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, Ju_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ \langle B_2y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, Jv_n - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = J^{-1}(\beta Ju_n + (1 - \beta)Jv_n), \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)\}, \\ x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{array} \right. \quad (40)$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and J is the normalized duality mapping on E ; $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ converges to some element of F .

If $E = H$, a Hilbert space, then E is 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space, in this case, continuous relatively nonexpansive mapping reduces to continuous quasi-nonexpansive mapping. Furthermore, $J = I$, identity operator on H and $\Pi_C = P_C$, projection mapping from H into C . Thus, the following corollaries hold.

Corollary 3. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be monotone continuous mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be finite family of continuous quasi-nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants $\gamma_i \in (0, 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{cases} x_0 \in C_0 = C, & \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ z_n = P_C(x_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1} x_n), \\ y_n = \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n) T_{n+1} z_n; u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \langle B_1 y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, u_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \langle B_2 y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, v_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = \beta u_n + (1 - \beta) v_n, \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \|z - w_n\| \leq \|z - x_n\|\}, \\ x_{n+1} = P_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{cases} \tag{41}$$

where $A_n = A_{n \pmod m}$, $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$; and $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in $[a, b]$ for some $0 < a < b < \frac{c^2 \gamma}{2}$, where c is the 2-uniformly convex constant of E and $\gamma = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} \gamma_i$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F .

Corollary 4. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be monotone continuous mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be finite family of continuous quasi-nonexpansive mappings. Let $F :=$

$$\left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$$

Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{cases} x_0 \in C_0 = C, & \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n) T_{n+1} x_n; u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \langle B_1 y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, u_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \langle B_2 y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, v_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = \beta u_n + (1 - \beta) v_n, \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \|z - w_n\| \leq \|z - x_n\|\}, \\ x_{n+1} = P_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{cases} \tag{42}$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F .

Corollary 5. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H . Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be finite family of continuous quasi-nonexpansive mappings. Let $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be monotone

continuous mappings. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 VI(B_k, C) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{cases} x_0 \in C_0 = C, & \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n) T_{n+1} x_n; u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ \langle B_1 y_n, y - u_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, u_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ \langle B_2 y_n, y - v_n \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, v_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = \beta u_n + (1 - \beta) v_n, \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \|z - w_n\| \leq \|z - x_n\|\}, \\ x_{n+1} = P_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{cases} \tag{43}$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F .

Corollary 6. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert space H . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4). Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be finite family of continuous quasi-nonexpansive mappings. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 EP(f_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\begin{cases} x_0 \in C_0 = C, & \text{chosen arbitrarily,} \\ y_n = \alpha_n x_n + (1 - \alpha_n) T_{n+1} x_n; u_n, v_n \in C \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_n, y) + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_n, u_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(v_n, y) + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - v_n, v_n - y_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = \beta u_n + (1 - \beta) v_n, \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \|z - w_n\| \leq \|z - x_n\|\}, \\ x_{n+1} = P_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{cases} \tag{44}$$

where $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F .

Note that, if, in Theorem 1, we replace

“ $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i^{-1}(0) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$ ” with “ $\|Ax\| \leq \|Ax - Ap\| \forall p \in F$, $x \in C$ and $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m VI(A_i, C) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$ ”, then we get the following theorem.

Theorem 3. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_1, f_2 : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_1, B_2 : C \rightarrow E^*$ be continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be a finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants $\gamma_i \in (0, 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m VI(A_i, C) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^2 GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by (13). Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ converges to some element of F .

Proof. Let $p \in F$. Then by assumption $\|Ax\| \leq \|Ax - Ap\| \forall x \in C$ and in particular $\|Ax\| \leq \|Ax - Ap\| = 0$ which implies that $Ap = 0$ and so $p \in A^{-1}(0)$. Therefore, the conclusion follows from Theorem 1. ■

The proof of the following theorem can be easily obtained from the method of proof of Theorem 1.

Theorem 4. Let C be a nonempty closed convex subset of 2-uniformly convex and uniformly smooth real Banach space E . Let $f_k : C \times C \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be finite family of bifunctions satisfying (A1) - (A4) and $B_k : C \rightarrow E^*$ $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ be finite continuous monotone mappings. Let $T_j : C \rightarrow C$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ be a finite family of continuous relatively nonexpansive mappings and $A_i : C \rightarrow E^*$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ be a finite family of γ_i -inverse strongly monotone operators with constants $\gamma_i \in (0, 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Let $F := \left[\bigcap_{j=1}^d F(T_j) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{i=1}^m VI(A_i, C) \right] \cap \left[\bigcap_{k=1}^q GEP(f_k, B_k) \right] \neq \emptyset$. Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence defined by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_0 \in C_0 = C, \text{ chosen arbitrarily,} \\ z_n = \Pi_C J^{-1}(Jx_n - \lambda_n A_{n+1}x_n), \\ y_n = J^{-1}(\alpha_n Jx_n + (1 - \alpha_n)JT_{n+1}z_n), u_{k,n} \in C, k = 1, 2, \dots, q \text{ s.t.} \\ f_1(u_{1,n}, y) + \langle B_1y_n, y - u_{1,n} \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_{1,n}, Ju_{1,n} - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ f_2(u_{2,n}, y) + \langle B_2y_n, y - u_{2,n} \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_{2,n}, Ju_{2,n} - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ \vdots \\ f_q(u_{q,n}, y) + \langle B_qy_n, y - u_{q,n} \rangle + \frac{1}{r_n} \langle y - u_{q,n}, Ju_{q,n} - Jy_n \rangle \geq 0, \forall y \in C, \\ w_n = J^{-1}(\beta_1Ju_{1,n} + \beta_2Ju_{2,n} + \dots + \beta_qJu_{q,n}), \\ C_{n+1} = \{z \in C_n : \phi(z, w_n) \leq \phi(z, x_n)\}, \\ x_{n+1} = \Pi_{C_{n+1}}(x_0), n \geq 0, \end{array} \right. \tag{45}$$

where $A_n = A_{n \pmod m}$, $T_n = T_{n \pmod m}$ and J is the normalized duality mapping on E ; $\{r_n\}_{n \geq 1} \subset [c_1, \infty)$ for some $c_1 > 0$, $\beta, \alpha_n \in (0, 1)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, q$ such that $\sum_{k=1}^q \beta_k, \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n(1 - \alpha_n) > 0$; and $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in $[a, b]$ for some $0 < a < b < \frac{c^2\gamma}{2}$, where c is the 2-uniformly convex constant of E and $\gamma = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} \gamma_i$. Then, the sequence $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F .

CONCLUSION

Corollary 1 improves Theorem 3.1 of Takahashi and Zembayashi [22] to a finite family of relatively nonexpansive mappings and equilibrium problems. Theorem 3.1 of Li and Su [6] is a special case of Theorem 3 in which $i = 1, k = 1, B_1 \equiv B_2 \equiv 0$ and $T_j \equiv I$ for all $j = 1, \dots, d$. Slight modifications of the iteration schemes studied in this paper extend the results of Ofoedu et al. [13] from Hilbert space to 2-uniformly convex Banach space. Our theorems improve and generalize the main results of Takahashi and Zembayashi [22], Li and Su [6], Ofoedu et al. [13] and several other results which are announced recently. Our iteration process, method of proof and corollaries are of independent interest.

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